
Study on Spatial Pattern and Corridor Construction of Cultural Heritage in Kaifeng City Based on MCR Model

Yuanzhi Huo

Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo 454003, China

Abstract: To systematically integrate cultural heritage resources and establish protection strategies in Kaifeng City, this study takes all 89 national and provincial cultural relic protection units in Kaifeng as research objects. Kernel density analysis is used to explore their spatial distribution characteristics, and the MCR model is applied to extract cultural heritage corridors. Furthermore, protection strategies based on cultural heritage corridors are discussed. The results show that: (1) Cultural heritage exhibits a clustered distribution, forming two high-density areas (the central urban area and the border area between Xiangfu District and Lankao County), and four sub-dense areas scattered in Xiangfu District, Weishi County and other districts and counties. (2) The heritage corridor presents a hierarchical structure of "main corridors + secondary corridors". The main corridors are cross-shaped across multiple districts and counties in a "n-shaped" pattern, while the secondary corridors are radial branches connecting partial regions, forming a hierarchical system of "main trunk bearing the core axis and branches extending characteristics". This study aims to provide a reference for the protection of cultural heritage in Kaifeng and similar cities.

Keywords: heritage corridor; cultural heritage; minimum cumulative resistance (MCR) model; Kaifeng City

1. Introduction

Cultural heritage, particularly national and provincial-level cultural relics protection units, serves as the core carrier for inheriting historical context, carrying rich historical information and artistic values accumulated during the development of the nation. As the core area of Song Dynasty culture, Kaifeng's national and provincial-level cultural relics protection units exhibit core characteristics of spatial correlation, agglomeration, and thematic cultural values specific to the Song Dynasty, constituting the natural foundation and suitable prerequisites for implementing integrated protection, utilization, and demonstration through the heritage corridor model.

As one of the first batch of national historical and cultural cities and the "Ancient Capital of Eight Dynasties," Kaifeng holds special sample value for cultural heritage protection. It possesses national-level cultural relics protection units such as the Northern Song Dynasty Dongjing City Site and the Youguo Temple Pagoda, bearing the development context of ancient Chinese capital cities and serving as a living museum for studying the evolution of Central Plains culture. However, its heritage protection has become urgent: the core area of the Northern Song Dynasty Dongjing City Site is fragmented by modern buildings and traffic arteries, becoming "isolated islands"[1], and the "city upon city" layered landscape faces the risk of dissolution. The dense distribution of cultural heritage yet fragmented protection, and the complete cultural context yet broken spatial connections, have become critical issues that need to be addressed for cultural continuity and regional high-quality development. The heritage corridor concept originated from the American greenway theory [2], with its core being the connection of individual heritage sites through historical routes to form linear cultural heritage landscape collections that can be protected as a whole. After the initiation of domestic research, Wang Zhifang *et al.* [3] first systematically defined this concept, emphasizing the reconstruction of spatial continuity of urban

historical landscapes through linear integration; Yu Kongjian *et al.* [4] proposed the "point-line-surface" systematic protection theory, laying the theoretical foundation for "from single-point protection to regional integration," promoting research from fragmented cognition to spatial system construction, breaking through the traditional single-object thinking of cultural relics protection, and establishing the cognitive connection between cultural heritage and spatial environment. With the development of GIS technology and spatial analysis models, heritage corridor research has entered the technical quantification stage. Yuan Yanhua *et al.* [5] applied the MCR model in the Luoyang case to construct corridor networks, achieving quantitative analysis of spatial correlations among heritage points and promoting research from theoretical conception to technical implementation; Wu Junyu *et al.* [6] combined territorial spatial planning to demarcate "core areas-buffer zones," solving the problem of protection scope delineation and promoting the connection between corridor planning and spatial governance systems; Wang Jiaca [7] used ArcGIS and the MCR model to form a quantitative paradigm, promoting technical methods toward multi-scale and cross-regional development. At the urban practice level, Wang Sisi *et al.* [8] summarized Beijing's experience in fragmented heritage governance; Zhu Qiang *et al.* [9] explored the quantitative path for canal corridor width in the Tianjin section, achieving the leap from method construction to specific scale definition; Yang Peifeng *et al.* [10] proposed the Dazhangxi corridor and cultural tourism integration strategy in Fuzhou, extending to the field of functional activation. In summary, heritage corridor research has made significant progress, but existing studies still have obvious shortcomings: First, insufficient technical adaptability—most focus on macro-regional scales, lacking targeted optimization for cities with high-density heritage, making it difficult for corridors to accurately reflect spatial correlations in dense areas; Second, lack of operability—there are no quantitative standards for corridor width and scope, and no systematic and feasible protection strategies. Based on this, this paper employs kernel density analysis and the MCR model to explore the spatial distribution characteristics of cultural heritage in Kaifeng City, construct cultural heritage corridors, and determine its systematic cultural heritage protection pattern from the perspective of territorial spatial planning, aiming to provide new ideas for cultural heritage protection in Kaifeng and similar cities.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Area Overview

Figure 1: Location map of the study area

Kaifeng City is located in central Henan Province, with the Yellow River and Huaihe River systems running through it. It has rivers with drainage areas exceeding 1,000 square kilometers, such as the Huiji and Jialu Rivers. The wetland ecosystem is highly intact, supporting a blue-green space system with three historical gardens including Longting Lake-Qingming Shanghe Yuan as the core, providing a good ecological foundation

for the development of cultural heritage resources. Kaifeng City possesses abundant cultural heritage resources and is one of the first batch of national historical and cultural cities. The Northern Song Dynasty Zhouqiao Site and the Tongji Canal Section of the Grand Canal have been selected among the "100 Major Archaeological Discoveries of the Century." Overall, Kaifeng City has good natural ecology and cultural heritage, with multiple important roads such as National Highways 106 and 310 intersecting, providing favorable conditions for constructing heritage corridors.

Data

The basic data used in this study mainly include spatial location data of cultural heritage in Kaifeng City and resistance factor data for minimum cumulative resistance calculation. Administrative division data comes from the Geospatial Data Cloud; cultural heritage data comes from the list of national and provincial-level cultural relics protection units published on the official website of Kaifeng Municipal Culture, Radio, Television and Tourism Bureau, with latitude and longitude coordinates of each cultural relics protection unit extracted using Baidu Map API tools. Resistance factor data mainly include elevation, land use type, roads, and slope of Kaifeng City. Elevation data uses ASTER GDEM 30m resolution data extracted from the Geospatial Data Cloud website; land use data comes from 30m×30m resolution land survey data published by the GlobalLand30 website; road data is obtained based on the OpenStreetMap platform; slope data is calculated using the slope analysis tool in ArcGIS 10.8 software with elevation data as the extraction object.

Kernel Density Estimation

Kernel density estimation calculates the density distribution characteristics of points in specific regions to analyze their spatial agglomeration characteristics. The specific formula is as follows:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n k\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where: k represents the kernel function, n is the total number of cultural heritage samples, h represents the preset radius, and $(x-x_i)$ represents the distance from point x to x_i .

Minimum Cumulative Resistance Model

The Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model was first applied to ecological corridor construction, aiming to simulate the minimum cost required for species to traverse landscapes with different resistance values. Yu Kongjian *et al.* applied this method to the suitability analysis of heritage corridors. The model formula is as follows:

$$MCR = \int \min \sum_{j=n}^{i=m} (D_{ij} \times R_i) \quad (2)$$

Where: MCR represents the minimum cumulative resistance value; f is its positive correlation with ecological processes; D_{ij} is the standardized resistance factor value; R_i is the weight of a single factor.

3. Results

Cultural Heritage Distribution Characteristics

Kernel density analysis was conducted on the spatial distribution of 89 cultural heritage source points in the ArcGIS platform. The results show that cultural heritage in Kaifeng City presents significant clustered distribution characteristics, forming two high-density areas and four sub-density areas (Figure 2). The first high-density area is located in the main urban area, with Shunhe District, Longting District, and Gulou District as the core, radiating to cover the northern part of Yuwangtai District and the western part of Xiangfu District. This area centrally carries national-level cultural relics protection units such as the Northern Song Dynasty Capital City Site. The second high-density area is located in the border zone between Xiangfu District and Lankao County in the northeastern part of the city, which is a dense area of Song-Yuan post road cultural heritage. The four sub-density areas are respectively located in western Xiangfu District, central Qixian County, northern Weishi County, and Weichuan Ancient Town, constituting secondary nodes of the city's heritage network.

The above dense areas concentrate most of the national-level cultural relics protection units in the city. Their high-density heritage overlay with historical city site spatial context systematically reflects Kaifeng's "city upon city" layered history and the core value of the ancient capital. They are key areas for heritage corridor construction and integrated protection, having typicality and spatial representativeness as core nodes for corridor construction, providing spatial basis for "prioritizing the connection of dense areas" in the subsequent corridor construction process.

Figure 2: Spatial Density Analysis of Cultural Heritage Origin Clusters in Kaifeng

Heritage Corridor Construction

Resistance factor selection needs to reflect the degree of obstruction that geographical environments pose to material circulation and cultural transmission between heritage points, and satisfy three principles: scientific validity, data quantifiability, and regional adaptability. Referencing domestic and international heritage corridor research, through field investigation and literature review, four types of resistance factors commonly used were finally determined: elevation, slope, land use type, and distance from roads. Elevation classification is based on DEM statistical characteristics of Kaifeng City, using the average value as the center and local data distribution as the basis, referencing the classification standards of Lin Yicheng *et al.* The higher the elevation, the greater the construction difficulty of the corridor and the greater the resistance. The overall slope of Kaifeng City is gentle, with slope classification using 3° intervals to highlight the impact of micro-topographic differences on corridor construction. The greater the slope, the higher the construction and maintenance costs of the corridor and the greater the resistance. According to the 100-meter visual accessible area of heritage source points, the 240-meter 3-minute walking comfort circle, the 400-meter basic width of heritage buffer zones (GB/T50357-2018), and the 600-meter walking limit threshold for cultural experience participants, the resistance value classification for road distance is determined. The closer to national and provincial highways, the higher the transportation convenience and the smaller the resistance to interaction and connection between heritage points. Land use type classification and assignment reference the classification standards in Yuan Yanhua's Luoyang case, with grassland types added based on the distribution of meadows in the Yellow River beach area of Kaifeng City. According to the resistance characteristics analysis of construction land with optimal facility accessibility, grassland with passable but vegetation-obstructed conditions, cultivated land with seasonal farming obstacles, woodland with visual and physical barriers, and water areas with complete barriers, five-level assignment standards are determined for different land use types.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to determine resistance factor weights. Eight experts in the fields of cultural heritage protection, GIS, and spatial planning were invited to conduct pairwise comparisons of factor importance using the 1-9 scale method. After constructing the judgment matrix, the weight vector was calculated and passed the consistency test (Table 2). Averaging the weight scores of the 8 experts, the final weights for each factor were: land use type 0.30, elevation 0.25, slope 0.25, and road distance 0.20.

Table 1: Consistency test results

Maximum Eigenvalue	CI Value	RI Value	CR Value	Consistency Test Result
4.021	0.00	0.89	0.00	通过
	7	0	8	

Table 2: Resistance Factor Weights and Assignments

Resistance Factor	Weight	Resistance Value				
		1	2	3	4	5
Elevation (m)	0.25	<63	63-70	70-79	79-93	>93
Slope (°)	0.25	<3	3-6	6-9	9-12	>12
Road Distance (m)	0.20	<100	100-240	240-400	400-600	>600
Land Use Type	0.30	Construction Land	Grassland	Cultivated Land	Woodland	Water Area

The four types of factor data were uniformly converted to the WGS1984 coordinate system and 30m×30m raster resolution data. Then, using the ArcGIS "Reclassify" tool, based on the classification and assignment standards in Table 3, each raster cell was converted to 1-5 level resistance value assignments according to the factor classification intervals, generating four single-factor resistance surfaces for elevation, road distance, slope, and land use type (Figure 3-a,b,c,d). From the spatial distribution of the comprehensive resistance surface: low resistance areas are mainly concentrated in the main urban area of Kaifeng City and along National Highways 106, 220 and Provincial Highways 313, 327. This area is mainly construction land, and due to its location in the Huang-Huai alluvial plain, all four types of resistance factors show low resistance characteristics, with the lowest comprehensive resistance values after superposition, becoming high-suitability areas for corridor construction; medium-low resistance areas are mainly distributed in the western part of Xiangfu District, northern Weishi County, and other suburban areas surrounding the main urban area. These areas are mainly cultivated land and grassland, with single-factor resistance at medium-low levels, and comprehensive resistance values slightly higher than the main urban area, constituting medium-high suitability areas for corridor construction; medium-high resistance areas are mainly distributed in central Qixian County, southern Lankao County, and other remote suburban areas, with woodland as the main land use type, medium-high single-factor resistance, and higher comprehensive resistance values, belonging to medium suitability areas for corridor construction; high resistance areas are mainly concentrated along the Yellow River, around large lakes, and in some areas with micro-topographic fluctuations. These areas are mainly water areas, with multi-factor high resistance superposition resulting in maximum comprehensive resistance values, becoming low suitability or unsuitable areas for corridor construction. Overall, the spatial distribution pattern of the comprehensive resistance surface in Kaifeng City presents a gradient characteristic of "low resistance in the center, increasing outward, high resistance in water areas."

Figure 3: Distribution of single-factor resistance surface and comprehensive resistance surfaces

Based on the above single factors, integrating attributes such as elevation, slope, distance from roads, and land use type, the comprehensive resistance surface was constructed. In ArcGIS 10.8, resistance surfaces for elevation, slope, road distance, and land use type were constructed through classified resistance values. Using the raster calculator in the "Spatial Analyst Tools" toolbox in ArcGIS, according to the resistance factor weights in Table 1, the four single resistance surfaces were weighted and superimposed to generate the comprehensive resistance surface map of cultural heritage in Kaifeng City (Figure 4). The minimum resistance paths between all source points were spatially superimposed on the basis of suitability zoning, finally identifying the potential cultural heritage corridor network covering Kaifeng City. This network is composed of minimum resistance paths between various heritage source points, providing quantitative basis for subsequent heritage corridor construction.

Based on the comprehensive resistance surface, in ArcGIS 10.8, the reclassify tool was used to divide the resistance surface analysis results into five areas: high, medium-high, medium, low, and unsuitable. Overall, areas with higher suitability are mainly concentrated along traffic arteries and urban built-up areas, while unsuitable areas are mostly distributed in water areas and mountainous hilly areas (Figure 4). Calculations show: the area and proportion of each region are high suitability area (2,527.18 km², 42.3%), medium-high suitability area (1,667.57 km², 27.9%), medium suitability area (958.48 km², 16.0%), low suitability area (594.74 km², 9.9%), and unsuitable area (231.18 km², 3.9%), showing a gradient decreasing characteristic of "high suitability > medium-high suitability > medium suitability > low suitability > unsuitable." High and medium-high suitability areas account for over 70%, concentrated in heritage resource-rich belts, possessing priority for corridor construction; medium suitability areas need to coordinate the balance between protection and utilization; low suitability areas have significant ecological sensitivity; unsuitable areas are fragmented in distribution due to natural constraints.

Figure 4: The proportion and area of potential corridors and suitable areas

Potential corridor identification is only the "minimum resistance path" at the theoretical level. It needs to be optimized for corridor routing combining actual spatial characteristics and functional needs to ensure the continuity, representativeness, and operability of corridor construction. Corridor routing optimization needs to follow these principles: First is continuity—potential corridors may be broken due to natural obstacles and artificial facilities, requiring topological repair combining actual road networks and water networks, repairing broken sections and eliminating redundant paths; second, maximizing heritage coverage needs to be considered, prioritizing paths that connect heritage dense areas; third, priority should be given to selecting paths through high-suitability areas of resistance paths and trying to couple with historical route spaces.

According to the above principles, the corridor routing is determined as a hierarchical structure of "main corridors + secondary corridors": The main corridor structure presents a "several"-shaped pattern, spatially crossing Weishi County-Tongxu County-Xiangfu District-Gulou District-Yuwangtai District-Longting District-Shunhe Hui District-Xiangfu District-Lankao County-Qixian County, connecting two high-density cultural

heritage areas and three sub-density areas, connecting core heritage points such as the Northern Song Dynasty Tokyo City Ruins and Youguo Temple Pagoda, strengthening the integrity of ancient capital cultural context and carrying the function of city-wide cultural radiation; secondary corridors are radial branches, connecting sub-density areas such as Weishi County and Qixian County, including two branches in northern Xiangfu District and Lankao County, the eastern Xiangfu District-Weishi County branch, and the western Qixian County-Tongxu County branch, supplementing coverage of peripheral heritage points, forming a hierarchical corridor routing system where "main corridors carry the cultural main axis and branch corridors extend regional characteristics." The distribution of main and secondary corridor routes is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Cultural heritage corridors and suitability zoning

Figure 6: Linear analysis of the number of heritage sites versus distance from major corridors

4. Conclusion

This study takes all 89 national and provincial-level cultural relics protection units in Kaifeng City as the research object, integrating kernel density analysis, Minimum Cumulative Resistance (MCR) model, and GIS spatial analysis technology to systematically explore the construction path of cultural heritage corridors. The main conclusions are as follows:

- (1) Cultural heritage in Kaifeng City shows cluster distribution, forming 2 high-density areas and 4 sub-density areas in space. The 2 high-density areas are located in the central urban area and the border zone between Xiangfu District and Lankao County, centrally carrying core heritage such as the Northern Song

Dynasty capital city ruins; the 4 sub-density areas are distributed in western Xiangfu District, central Qixian County, northern Weishi County, and Weichuan Ancient Town, constituting secondary nodes of the heritage network.

- (2) The cultural heritage corridor routes in Kaifeng City show a hierarchical structure of "main corridors + secondary corridors." The main corridors present a "several"-shaped pattern across multiple districts/counties, connecting core heritage points and high-density areas, strengthening the ancient capital cultural context and radiation function; secondary corridors are radial branches, connecting sub-density areas, supplementing peripheral heritage points, forming a hierarchical system where "main corridors carry the main axis and branch corridors extend characteristics."

References

- [1]. Wang Yuncai, Han Liying. Protection Mode of Traditional Regional Cultural Landscape Based on Landscape Island Analysis—A Case Study of Luzhi Town, Suzhou City, Jiangsu Province[J]. Geographical Research, 2014, 33(01): 143-156.
- [2]. Gong Daode, Yuan Xiaoyuan, Zhang Qingping. Analysis on the Operation Mechanism of American Canal National Heritage Corridor Model and Its Enlightenment to the Protection and Development of Large Linear Cultural Heritage in China[J]. Urban Development Studies, 2016, 23(01): 17-22.
- [3]. Wang Zhifang, Sun Peng. Heritage Corridor—A Relatively New Heritage Protection Method[J]. Chinese Landscape Architecture, 2001, (05): 86-89.
- [4]. Li Wei, Yu Kongjian, Li Dihua. Heritage Corridor and the Theoretical Framework for the Integrated Protection of the Grand Canal[J]. Urban Problems, 2004, (01): 28-31+54.
- [5]. Yuan Yanhua, Xu Jiangang, Zhang Xiang. Research on the Construction of Urban Heritage Corridor Network Based on Suitability Analysis—A Case Study of Ancient Capital Luoyang[J]. Remote Sensing Information, 2014, 29(03): 117-124.
- [6]. Wu Junyu, Chen Kangfu, Chen Jingwen, *et al.* Research on the Construction of Cultural Heritage Corridors in Jiangmen City from the Perspective of Territorial Spatial Planning[J]. Journal of Human Settlements in West China, 2020, 35(01): 7-16.
- [7]. Wang Jiacan, Zhang Hongyan, Xie Congying, *et al.* Suitability Evaluation of Intangible Cultural Heritage Corridor Construction in the Grand Canal Cultural Belt Based on GIS[J]. Acta Ecologica Sinica, 2025, 45(11): 5322-5339.
- [8]. Wang Sisi, Li Ting, Dong Yin. Spatial Structure Analysis of Cultural Heritage and Construction of Heritage Corridor Network in Beijing[J]. Journal of Arid Land Resources and Environment, 2010, 24(06): 51-56.
- [9]. Zhu Qiang. Construction of Industrial Heritage Corridor in the Southern Section of the Beijing-Hangzhou Grand Canal[D]. Peking University, 2007.
- [10]. Yang Peifeng, Lu Yating, Yang Di, *et al.* Protection and Activation of Cultural Heritage from the Perspective of Heritage Corridor—A Case Study of the Fuzhou Section along Dazhangxi River[J]. Planners, 2024, 40(05): 123-130.

